
Behavioral Economics in Online Shopping: The Psychology of Discounts and Flash Sales

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1.1 Introduction

The rapid growth of e-commerce industry among the people has paved the way for online purchasing. Online shopping is the activity or action of buying products or services over the Internet. It means using the internet, finding a seller's website, choosing an item and setting up delivery. The buyer can pay for the goods or services online with a credit or debit card or in person when the product is delivered. The term does not only include online purchases but also searching the product through online. Online shopping has been around for about twenty-five years. But its popularity has greatly increased. Today, we can buy almost anything in online. Numerous discounts and flash sales were available while entering online shopping. So, the people engaged impulsive and unplanned purchase. In fact, retail experts say that online shopping will soon overtake traditional shopping in monetary terms. This paper is an attempt to examine the Behavioral Economics in Online Shopping: The Psychology of Discounts and Flash Sales.

1.2 Buying attitude towards online shoppers

The world is rapidly becoming a Global Village due to Internet. The internet changed the landscape of the retail industry and the rules of the game in retailing are fast changing. Our Indian society has also affected by the western culture in each and every aspect. Both in urban areas and in regular cities, life is getting faster. Some other factors like time constraints, travel congestion, late work hours, the convenience of card money and most importantly, the availability of the internet at anyone's doorstep. Traffic jams, late working hours, versatility of plastic money and above all the approach of internet at the door step. Online retailers have improved their service and are providing more and more convenience to the customers. From advance payment options they moved on to payment on delivery. From fixed delivery timings they have moved on to convenient delivery timings at the choice of the customer.

The people used online shopping for purchase anything like groceries, gadgets and gifts to clothes, vehicles and cruises. The online shop are available at 24/7, more convenient to buy any products and also compare the products on the basis of product reviews from customers, access vendor returns policies and find warranty information. They are unable to see, touch, feel, smell, or experience the things they wish to buy, consumers find it challenging to evaluate them and make decisions about what to buy when they shop online. In addition, some products, like clothing and shoes, must be tried before being purchased; but, while shopping online, it is impossible to inspect, feel and evaluate the quality of the products before making a purchase, which makes buyers reluctant to buy. The primary thing that concerns consumers when making purchases online is product quality. Additionally, online purchasing has a higher rate of counterfeit and copied goods. The most frequent reason why customers steer clear of online purchases is a lack of trust in the online seller.

1.3 Statement of the problem

Online shopping is increasingly replacing traditional purchasing methods among consumers. One popular marketing tactic used by e-commerce platforms to boost sales is flash sales. These limited-time offers encourage impulsive, unplanned, and urgent purchases. While flash sales can significantly increase short-term sales, they also raise concerns regarding consumer awareness, pre-purchase satisfaction, and ethical business practices. Many online shoppers feel pressured by limited-time deals, countdown timers, and instant discounts, which often lead to impulsive purchases without proper evaluation or genuine need. Despite the growing popularity of flash sales, there is limited understanding of how these tactics influence and affect consumers' long-term purchasing habits. Given this context, it is important to explore the factors that drive impulse buying during flash sales and how these influences shape consumer behavior over time.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

- To know the profile of the online shoppers
- To identify psychological drivers like urgency, scarcity and FOMO (Fear Of Missing Out) in impulse buying.
- To analysis of psychological drivers towards discounts and flash sales in online shopping and the gender of the respondents

1.5 Research Methodology

The present study is conducted in Sivakasi city using 300 respondents. The study is based on primary data and to collect a questionnaire was constructed covering all details in the objective for the study. The data is collected employing convenient sampling method. Percentage analysis, Garrett Ranking Method and T-test are used to analyses the data.

1.6 Data Analysis and Interpretation

The profile of online buyers, Frequency of online purchasing, attitude towards discounts and flash sales related data are collected and analyzed.

1.6.1 Profile of online buyers

Profile of online buyers are needed in order to analysis the buying attitude of online shopping. The information about profile of online shoppers like Gender, Age, Profession and monthly income of the respondents are displayed in Table.1.

Table 1
Profile of online buyers

Profile	Category	No.of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	120	40.00
	Female	180	60.00
	Total	300	100.00
Age	Below 20	45	15.00
	20-40	75	25.00

	40-60	120	40.00
	Above 60	60	20.00
	Total	300	100.00
Profession	Business	45	15.00
	Employees	75	25.00
	House Wife	120	40.00
	Students	60	20.00
	Total	300	100.00
Monthly Income	Below Rs.10,000	25	8.33
	Rs.10,000-Rs.20,000	20	6.67
	Rs.20,000 – Rs.30,000	75	25.00
	Above Rs.30,000	180	60.00
	Total	300	100.00

Source: Primary Data

From the above analysis, it is inferred that out of 300 respondent's majority of 60.00 per cent of the respondents are female, 40.00 per cent of the respondents are in the age between 40–60 years, 40.00 per cent of the respondents are House wife, and 60.00 per cent of the respondents are earned above Rs.30,000 as monthly income.

1.6.2 Frequency of online purchasing

Consumers are shopping online more frequently. The frequency with which consumers shop online is accelerating. Table 2 shows the frequency of online purchasing.

Table 2
Frequency of online purchasing

Frequency	No.of Respondents	Percentage
Regularly	115	38.33
Occasionally	110	36.67

Rarely	75	25.00
Total	300	100.00

Source: Primary Data

From the above analysis, it is inferred that out of 300 respondents 38.33 per cent of the respondents are regularly using online app while purchasing the product, 36.67 per cent of the respondents are used the online app occasionally and the remaining 25.00 per cent of the respondents are rarely used. From the analysis it is noted that most of the respondents are using online app for regularly.

1.6.3 Psychological Drivers towards Discounts and Flash Sales in Online Shopping

Shopping online is much better than going into stalls and shops to buy goods and ask for services to be rendered because it saves a lot of time. The psychological drivers towards discount and flash sales in online shopping shows in Table 3.

Table 3
Psychological Drivers Towards Discounts and Flash Sales in Online Shopping

Psychological Drivers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	Total
Discount and Flash sales can provide an opportunity to purchase higher-priced items at low price	96	40	11	38	10	20	25	11	12	13	24	300
Discount and Flash Sales creates Excitement and Urgency.	88	65	13	22	30	12	15	9	10	24	12	300
Discount and Flash Sales makes quick decisions to avoid missing out on a deal.	75	59	32	20	38	12	16	15	9	10	14	300
Discount and Flash Sales chose a brand they hadn't previously considered	65	68	29	18	25	15	12	16	20	24	8	300
Discount and Flash sales can lead to impulsive purchases	75	76	36	13	11	20	18	15	8	12	16	300
Discount and Flash sales	58	38	34	22	16	18	16	45	28	15	10	300

and discounts make me Buying unplanned items												
Discount and Flash sales create regret and dissatisfaction.	75	64	28	8	4	6	10	15	12	30	48	300
Discount and Flash sales can lead to over spending	68	72	52	7	5	26	22	18	15	10	5	300
Discount and Flash Sales creates the <u>excitement and pleasure</u> of shopping.	55	49	33	22	25	18	12	26	16	30	14	300
Discount and Flash sales perceived <u>urgency</u> and <u>time pressure</u>	54	66	38	18	14	12	15	22	20	25	16	300
Discount and Flash sales provides excitement of securing a discount and saving money	78	46	32	14	20	30	23	22	12	8	15	300

Source: Primary Data

Based on the above details the following part of the analysis is made.

Garret scores

The Garret ranks are calculated by using appropriate Garret ranking formula. Then based on the Garret ranks, the Garret table value is ascertained. The Garret table values and scores of each rank are multiplied to record scores. Finally, by adding each row, the total Garret score is obtained. The ranking result is presented in the following Table 4.

**Table 4
Ranking Results**

S.No	Psychological Drivers	Total Score	Rank	Average Score
1.	Discount and Flash sales can provide an opportunity to purchase higher-priced items at low price	18507	IV	52.95
2.	Discount and Flash Sales creates Excitement and Urgency	18999	III	53.64
3.	Discount and Flash Sales makes quick decisions to avoid missing out on a deal.	16341	XI	42.64

4.	Discount and Flash Sales chose a brand they hadn't previously considered	18327	V	51.43
5.	Discount and Flash sales can lead to impulsive purchases	19019	I	56.17
6.	Discount and Flash sales and discounts make me Buying unplanned items	17205	IX	47.64
7.	Discount and Flash sales create regret and dissatisfaction.	17066	X	45.53
8.	Discount and Flash sales can lead to over spending	19086	II	55.34
9.	Discount and Flash Sales creates the excitement and pleasure of shopping.	17275	VIII	47.14
10.	Discount and Flash sales perceived urgency and time pressure	17441	VII	48.51
11.	Discount and Flash sales provides excitement of securing a discount and saving money	18290	VI	50.00

Source: Computed Data

The above table shows the Garret scores and the average scores for each respondent. The average scores are ranked according to their values. The first rank is given to “Discount and Flash sales can lead to impulsive purchases”, second rank goes to “Discount and Flash sales can lead to over spending”, third rank is for the “Discount and Flash Sales creates Excitement and Urgency”, fourth rank is taken by “Discount and Flash sales can provide an opportunity to purchase higher-priced items at low price”, fifth rank goes to “Discount and Flash Sales chose a brand they hadn't previously considered”, sixth rank goes to “Discount and Flash sales provides excitement of securing a discount and saving money”, the seventh rank is given to “Discount and Flash sales perceived [urgency](#) and [time pressure](#)”, eighth rank goes to “Discount and Flash Sales creates the [excitement and pleasure](#) of shopping.”, ninth rank is for the “Discount and Flash sales and discounts make me Buying unplanned items”, tenth rank is taken by “Discount and Flash sales create regret and dissatisfaction.” and eleventh rank goes to “Discount and Flash Sales makes quick decisions to avoid missing out on a deal.”. It is inferred that the majority (56.17) of the college students are facing challenges of using technology in education.

1.6.4 Analysis of Psychological Drivers towards Discounts and Flash Sales in Online Shopping and the gender of the respondents

The investigator has classified the online shoppers based on their gender into two categories namely male and female and made analysis to know whether these two categories of the online shoppers are varied in their psychological drivers towards discounts and flash sales in online shopping of the respondents. The following null hypothesis is framed for this analysis.

Hypothesis

The online shoppers do not differ in their psychological drivers towards discounts and flash sales in online shopping when they are classified on the basis of the gender. To test this null hypothesis independent sample ‘t’ test is applied and the results are shown in the following Table 5.

Table 5

Gender and Psychological Drivers Towards Discounts and Flash Sales in Online Shopping – Group statistics

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Psychological Drivers	Gender of Respondents	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Discount and Flash sales can provide an opportunity to purchase higher-priced items at low price	Male	120	3.5917	1.21956	.11133
	Female	180	3.8556	1.04171	.07764
Discount and Flash Sales creates Excitement and Urgency.	Male	120	3.5833	1.21326	.11075
	Female	180	3.8333	1.05967	.07898
Discount and Flash Sales makes quick decisions to avoid missing out on a deal.	Male	120	3.5667	1.20037	.10958
	Female	180	3.8500	1.03824	.07739
Discount and Flash Sales chose a brand they hadn't previously considered	Male	120	3.5750	1.20686	.11017
	Female	180	3.8333	1.05967	.07898
Discount and Flash sales can lead to impulsive purchases	Male	120	3.2417	1.22300	.11164
	Female	180	3.7556	1.08119	.08059
Discount and Flash sales and discounts make me Buying unplanned items	Male	120	3.2500	1.23159	.11243
	Female	180	3.7278	1.11781	.08332
Discount and Flash sales create regret and dissatisfaction.	Male	120	3.2333	1.22806	.11211
	Female	180	3.8556	1.02004	.07603
Discount and Flash sales can lead to over spending	Male	120	3.2417	1.22985	.11227
	Female	180	3.8444	1.04010	.07752
Discount and Flash Sales creates the <u>excitement and pleasure</u> of shopping.	Male	120	3.4000	1.22577	.11190
	Female	180	3.8556	1.04171	.07764
Discount and Flash sales	Male	120	3.4000	1.22577	.11190

perceived <u>urgency</u> and <u>time pressure</u>	Female	180	3.8722	1.01953	.07599
Discount and Flash sales provides excitement of securing a discount and saving money	Male	120	3.2500	1.23159	.11243
	Female	180	3.8722	1.01953	.07599

Source: Primary Data

From the above table it is found that there is a difference between the mean and standard deviation values of the **Psychological Drivers Towards Discounts and Flash Sales in Online Shopping** when they are classified based on their gender. The result of Levene's Test for Equality of Variances obtained for this analysis is exhibited in the following Table 6.

Table 6

Gender and Psychological Drivers Towards Discounts and Flash Sales in Online Shopping Outcome of Independent sample 't' test

Psychological Drivers	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Diff.	Std. Error Diff.	
Discount and Flash sales can provide an opportunity to purchase higher-priced items at low price	*	10.072	.002	-2.006	298	.046	-.26389	.13154
	**			-1.944	227.186	.053	-.26389	.13573
Discount and Flash Sales creates Excitement and Urgency.	*	8.061	.005	-1.888	298	.060	-.25000	.13241
	**			-1.838	231.083	.067	-.25000	.13603
Discount and Flash Sales makes quick decisions to avoid missing out on a deal.	*	8.883	.003	-2.174	298	.030	-.28333	.13032
	**			-2.112	229.369	.036	-.28333	.13411

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Discount and Flash Sales chose a brand they hadn't previously considered	*	7.630	.006	-1.956	298	.051	-.25833	.13208
	**			-1.906	232.014	.058	-.25833	.13556
Discount and Flash sales can lead to impulsive purchases	*	6.312	.013	-3.825	298	.000	-.51389	.13434
	**			-3.732	233.219	.000	-.51389	.13769
Discount and Flash sales and discounts make me Buying unplanned items	*	4.591	.033	-3.481	298	.001	-.47778	.13725
	**			-3.414	237.896	.001	-.47778	.13993
Discount and Flash sales create regret and dissatisfaction.	*	15.357	.000	-4.766	298	.000	-.62222	.13056
	**			-4.594	222.367	.000	-.62222	.13546
Discount and Flash sales can lead to over spending	*	14.051	.000	-4.568	298	.000	-.60278	.13196
	**			-4.418	225.461	.000	-.60278	.13644
Discount and Flash Sales creates the <u>excitement and pleasure</u> of shopping.	*	12.946	.000	-3.455	298	.001	-.45556	.13186
	**			-3.345	226.303	.001	-.45556	.13620
Discount and Flash sales perceived <u>urgency</u> and <u>time</u>	*	15.312	.000	-3.621	298	.000	-.47222	.13040

pressure	**			-3.491	222.600	.001	-.47222	.1352 6
Discount and Flash sales provides excitement of securing a discount and saving money	*	15.745	.000	-4.760	298	.000	-.62222	.1307 1
	**			-4.585	221.794	.000	-.62222	.1357 0

Source: Computed Data

Note: * - Equal Variances Assumed

** - Equal Variances Not Assumed

The above result of Levene's test for equality of variances indicates that the online shoppers do not differ in their view about the eleven statements namely Discount and Flash sales can provide an opportunity to purchase higher-priced items at low price, **Discount and Flash Sales creates Excitement and Urgency**, Discount and Flash Sales makes quick decisions to avoid missing out on a deal, Discount and Flash Sales chose a brand they hadn't previously considered, Discount and Flash sales can lead to impulsive purchases, Discount and Flash sales and discounts make me Buying unplanned items, Discount and Flash sales create regret and dissatisfaction, Discount and Flash sales can lead to over spending, Discount and Flash Sales creates the [excitement and pleasure](#) of shopping, Discount and Flash sales perceived [urgency](#) and [time pressure and](#) Discount and Flash sales provides excitement of securing a discount and saving money. That is the probability value for these eleven aspects is more than the acceptance level of 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis framed for this analysis is not rejected and it is concluded that there is no significant association between gender of the online shoppers and their psychological drivers towards discounts and flash sales in online shopping. It is inferred that the online shoppers selected for the study do not varied in their view Discount and Flash sales can provide an opportunity to purchase higher-priced items at low price, **Discount and Flash Sales creates Excitement and Urgency**, Discount and Flash Sales makes quick decisions to avoid missing out on a deal, Discount and Flash Sales chose a brand they hadn't previously considered, Discount and Flash sales can lead to impulsive purchases, Discount and Flash sales and discounts make me Buying unplanned items, Discount and Flash sales create regret and dissatisfaction, Discount and Flash sales can lead to over spending, Discount and Flash Sales creates the [excitement and pleasure](#) of shopping, Discount and Flash sales perceived [urgency](#) and [time pressure and](#) Discount and Flash sales provides excitement of securing a discount and saving money.

1.7 Suggestions

The results of this study also provide information to the Government in order to play a role in regulating and enforcing the law in all online shopping events to ensure the safety of online shoppers. Government and communities need to pay attention to the online shopping model and their promotional strategies. The Government should take regulatory measures to safeguard the online shoppers from unfair discount and flash sales. So that the online shoppers can enjoy more advanced online shopping facilities.

1.8 Conclusion

The main strategies used by online shoppers, such as instilling a sense of urgency and scarcity, which engenders a fear of losing out, cause them to make snap decisions. The internet shoppers selected a brand that they had not before thought about. By changing reference points, customers are led to believe that bargains are worth more than the true value of the product. Discount and flash sales can result in overspending and impulsive shopping leads to the purchase of unforeseen things. These strategies, which are bolstered by user experience design and a positive economic gain, raise arousal and enjoyment.

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